

Appendix

Instagrammable Data: Using Visuals to Showcase More Than Numbers on AJ Labs Instagram Page

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Dimension	Categories	Options
Basic features	Date of publication	« Month Year »
	Type	Video, Photo, Album (Carrousel)
	Authors	Yes, No
	Topic (News beat)	Business Crime Culture Development/Government Education Environment Health Politics Population Science Science

		Social Issues Sports Technology
	Description	Yes, No
	Description length (words/characters)	« Number »
	Use of URLs	Yes, No
Data source	Provision of data source	Yes, No
	Number of data source	« Number »
	Country of origin	« List »
	Data provider	National Government International Government International Agencies Civic Society Groups/NGOs Academic Multiples Own data
Data visualization	Visualization type	Chart Drawing Map Photos Tiled cartogram

		Timeline Infographic (combination of charts/maps and visual elements)
	Tools used	Carto Infogram Mapbox Flourish Graphic design software Map4News Google Maps Unidentified NA (Not applied/Not available)
	Level of interactivity	Play Scroll right Zoom in Incentive to like No interactivity
	Number of visualizations	« Number »
Audiences	Likes	« Number »
	Comments	« Number »
	Views	« Number »
	Interactions	« Number »

Form and content	Purpose	Call-to-action Expand knowledge Inform the audience Promote (showcase project) Traffic (attract the reader to website)
	Story format	Additional information Explanatory Informative Projection Special Summary
	Text caption to complement the information	Yes, No
	Number of Hashtags	« Number »
	Ratio Hashtags/Post	« Number »
	Use of URLs	Yes, No

Table 1. Categories of evaluation were inspired by the works of Vázquez-Herrero et al. (2019), Tandoc & Oh (2017), Stalph (2018), and Young et al. (2018).